

**Validation of the Reading the Mind in the Eyes Test in a healthy Spanish sample
and women with Anorexia Nervosa**

Running head: The RMET in a Spanish sample

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Abstract

Introduction: The aim of this study was to build a Spanish version of the Reading the Mind in the Eyes Test (RMET) including limited time of response and an integrated glossary, and to test its validity. **Methods:** A total of 433 university students (121 men and 350 women) and 38 anorexic women completed the RMET and other related measures of empathy and alexithymia. The results of the Parallel Analysis (PA) suggested a unidimensional structure for 19 items, which was verified through a Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). Similarly to other research, this factor had a low reliability ($\alpha = .56$, $\rho = .59$); however, regarding validity, the total score of the instrument showed positive correlations with empathy and negatives with alexithymia. Furthermore, healthy females were superior to males in RMET, and to anorexic women; but no significant differences appeared between healthy men and the anorexic group. **Conclusion:** this study confirms the validity of the test and permits a relatively short and inexpensive means of administration in large samples of adults. Besides, it suggests the necessity of assessing and treating theory of mind in anorecxic women.

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Introduction

According to the authors that first proposed the term “Theory of Mind” (ToM; Premack & Woodruff, 1978) mental states are abstract entities (thoughts, feelings, intentions) that are inferred through observing people’s behaviour. In further studies, Baron-Cohen and Cross (1992) demonstrated that these can also be recognised by observing facial expressions. Specifically, these authors stated the existence of a “language of the eyes or gaze”, and that this area transmits enough information to understand people’s mental states (Baron-Cohen, Wheelwright, & Jolliffe, 1997).

With the aim of developing instruments to detect dysfunctions in these abilities, Baron-Cohen et al (1997) created an advanced test to assess ToM. The Reading the Mind in the Eyes (RME; Baron-Cohen, Jolliffe, Mortimore, & Robertson, 1997) evaluates one’s ability to read the intentions, feelings, and thoughts of others through facial expressions, specifically in the region of the eyes. Although conceived as an advanced ToM test, it is also used to assess emotion recognition (Baron-Cohen, Wheelwright, Hill, Raste, & Plumb, 2001). The first version of the test included 25 photographs of the eye-regions of men and women, and asked participants to choose which of 2 words best described what the person in the photograph was thinking or feeling. The words referred both to simple mental states, such as “happy” and to more complex ones, such as “arrogant” (Adams et al., 2010).

The original version of the RME exhibited some limitations. Firstly, the reduced number of items and the type of response (dichotomous response) rendered the task too simple, leading to “ceiling effects” that precluded the detection of individual differences. Furthermore, the original version had more female faces than male faces, and it was unclear if this may have biased the test in some way. Finally, there were doubts about the fact that comprehension of the words themselves might influence test scores (Baron-Cohen, Wheelwright et al., 2001). In order to solve all these problems, a new version was created, “The Reading the Mind in the Eyes Test Revised Version” (RMET; Baron-Cohen et al., 2001). In this revised version, the total number of items was increased to 36, and the number of response options (force-choice words) was increased to 4, reducing the random percentage of correct responses to 25%. Also, the number of male and female faces in the photographs was balanced to equal, and all the items were limited only to complex mental states in order to increase the likelihood of obtaining a greater range of performance in participants. Moreover, a glossary of all the mental state terms was included, so that subjects could consult the documentation, as to the meaning of a word, if they were unsure,

The authors of the new version explain that the complexity of analysis that this test requires makes it useful and appropriate for people with and without psychopathology and that it is sensitive enough to reveal subtle individual differences in ToM (Baron-Cohen et al., 2001).

To date, there are both paper and pencil and computerized versions of the RMET that are able to account for response times and for some other visual cues used in neuroimaging studies (Harkness, Sabbagh, Jacobson, Chowdrey, & Chen, 2005; Sanvicente-Vieira et al., 2014). However, to our knowledge, there are still no practical and cost-effective versions that permit the study of ToM in large collective Spanish samples with limited response times. The original version of the RMET is a costly and time-consuming test that requires a long time in administration, printing glossaries and long test protocols. Therefore, more useful or practical versions of the RMET would be necessary to use them with research purposes.

Studies using the RMET have revealed important deficits in ToM in patients suffering from schizophrenia (De Achával et al., 2010), autism (Baron-Cohen, 2009), social anxiety (Machado-de-Sousa et al., 2010), bipolar disorder (Derntl, Seidel, Kryspin-Exner, Hasmann, & Dobmeier, 2009) and borderline personality disorder (Frick et al., 2012), showing lower scores when compared to normal controls. This fact is consistent with these conditions that are actually characterised by having difficulty in processing information about social interactions in a broad sense. Research into eating disorders (EDs) is particularly important here, as most has revealed that these patients have worse results in ToM tasks. For instance, one study that examined performance of 72 female participants (AN N=24; BN=24; healthy controls N=24) on RMET reported that patients with AN had a poorer performance on this test compared to BN patients and healthy controls (De Sampaio et al., 2013). Moreover, a recent systematic review of ToM and eating disorders concluded that these patients had a poorer understanding of the mental states of others, as compared with controls (Caglar-Nazali et al., 2014). Similarly, another review that analyzed mentalization (a concept that includes, but is not limited to ToM) and its association with eating pathology in children and adolescents, found emotion recognition difficulties in adolescent samples with eating disorders, particularly in AN patients (Jewell et al., 2016).

On the other hand, most studies run in different countries have shown that females score significantly higher than men on the RMET (Hallerbäck, Lugnegård, Hjärthag, & Gillberg, 2009; Vellante et al., 2013; Voracek & Dressler, 2006; Yildirim et al., 2011), although others have not accounted for those differences (Cook & Saucier, 2010; Harkness, Jacobson, Duong, & Sabbagh, 2010). In a recent meta-analysis, Vellante et al. (2013), reported that in 6 out of the 17 studies tested, there were significant differences in favour of women (with a Cohen *d* ranging from .22 to .94), although in a significant number of them, there was no data referring to this.

Nowadays, there are widely used versions of the RMET adapted to many languages (for more information check ARC website: <https://www.autismresearchcentre.com/arctests>), and completed processes of validation have been conducted with Turkish (Yildirim et al., 2011), Italian (Vellante et al., 2013) and French (Prevost et al., 2014) populations. All of them have reported good psychometric properties.

Nevertheless, the great majority of the studies with the RMET do not report on the reliability of the instrument. Those that report on test-retest reliability show good stability of the scores (Prevost et al., 2014; Vellante et al., 2013; Yildirim et al., 2011)

with values ranging from .65 and .83. However, when Cronbach's alpha is calculated, low scores are obtained (Harkness et al., 2010; Yildirim et al., 2011). Furthermore, studies that include empathy measures to evaluate convergent validity of the RMET, have shown correlations with the Empathy Quotient (Alaerts, Nackaerts, Meyns, Swinnen, & Wenderoth, 2011; Carroll & Chiew, 2006; Cook & Saucier, 2010) but not with the Interpersonal Reactivity Index (Muller et al., 2010).

With respect to the factorial structure of the RMET, this has usually been interpreted in terms of a unifactorial scale summing all the items to get a total score; however, this structure has only been formally investigated in a study conducted by Vellante et al. (2013), which showed positive evidence of this. Interestingly, some studies have added subscales to the original version. The most common subdivision consists of splitting the items into positive, negative and neutral emotions (Maurage et al., 2011), although the psychometric properties of this procedure have not been officially recognized (Vellante et al., 2013).

When this process of validation started, there was no validated Spanish version of the test. Recently, Fernández-Abascal, Fernández-Berrocal, & Baron-Cohen (2013), have validated a version with undergraduates between 18 and 65 years. Despite the good results they obtained, the authors recommend investigating the possible correlation between RMET and other objective measures of emotion recognition, empathy and emotional intelligence, and to also analyse possible gender differences, as other previous validation studies have done before (Fernández-Abascal et al., 2013).

Taking all this into consideration, further research must be conducted to investigate the psychometric properties of RMET in the Spanish population because:

- a) None of the studies has formally investigated its factorial structure with this population.
- b) Including a clinical sample of those characterized as having problems with ToM and emotion recognition, such as anorexic patients do, would strengthen the results of the validation.
- c) The design and the characteristics of the RMET make it complex and costly to use with large samples because of the unlimited time to respond to each item and the different rhythms of response that subjects may have, and due to the number of glossaries that must be printed. Therefore, it seems necessary to validate more useful, practical and economical versions of the test.

To overcome these issues, the present study aimed to:

- a) Build an adapted version of the RMET that included a limited response time for the items and an integrated glossary of terms in order to facilitate its application in large samples.
- b) Explore its validity in young adults using different parameters: factorial analysis (initially, a three factor structure with positive, negative and neutral emotions

- was hypothesized) and associations with other measures (positive correlations with empathy measures and negatives with alexithymia were expected).
- c) Evaluate gender differences and differences between a healthy female sample and an anorexic female sample. Healthy women were expected to score higher than both healthy men and anorexic women.

Methods

Participants

Normative Sample

A total of 433 university students (121 men and 350 women) from different faculties at the University of the Basque Country (Spain) participated in the study. Their mean age was 20.0 ($SD=2.05$) years. All participants were Caucasian and from middle-class backgrounds. 97.3% had Spanish nationality. Of the participants, 85.2% came from two-parent families, 10.2% had divorced parents, 4.6% came from a family in which one of the parents had died. With regard to parental educational level, 61.6% of the participants' fathers and 57.9% of the mothers received education beyond a high school diploma (of which 38.4% and 38.1%, respectively, had obtained a university degree), 21.1% of the participants' fathers and 25.1% of the mothers had a high school diploma, and 17.3% and 17%, respectively, did not obtain a high school diploma.

Clinical Sample

The *ED sample* comprised 38 female inpatients aged 13 to 30 years. The mean age was 21.9 ($SD=5.30$). All them were receiving psychological treatment in the Basque Public Health System and in different national treatment associations and met the criteria for a full-blown *DSM-IV-TR* (American Psychiatric Association, 2000) diagnosis of anorexia (AN- restrictive or purgative). All participants were from middle-class backgrounds. 97.7% had Spanish nationality. With regard to family composition; 86.8% came from two-parent families, 10.5% had divorced parents and 2.7% came from a family in which one of the parents had died. Parental educational level was very similar to those of the participants in the Normative Sample.

Instruments

The revised version of the *Reading the Mind in the Eyes Test* (RMET; Baron-Cohen et al., 2001) was used for this validation. The RMET consists of 36 grey-scale photos of people in which only the area around the eyes can be seen. Each photo is surrounded by four mental state terms and the participant is instructed to choose the word best describing what the person in the photo is thinking or feeling. Only one of the four responses is deemed correct. Responses are coded as 0 (incorrect) and 1(correct) giving a maximum score of 36.

Alexithymia was assessed with the 20-item self-reported *Toronto Alexithymia Scale* (TAS-20; Bagby, Parker, & Taylor, 1994). The TAS scale consists of three subscales: Difficulty Identifying Feelings (DIF), Difficulty Describing Feelings (DDF) and Externally Oriented Thinking (EOT), (Parker, Michael Bagby, Taylor, Endler, & Schmitz, 1993). Each item is ranked on a five-point Likert scale and a higher score indicates higher levels of alexithymia. The TAS-20 has been translated and validated in numerous countries and languages, and is used worldwide, allowing comparisons of results (Taylor, Bagby, & Parker, 2003). The Spanish version of the TAS-20 (Martínez-Sánchez, 1996) has shown similar psychometric qualities to the original TAS-20, high internal consistency (Cronbach= 0.78) and test-retest reliability ($r= 0.71$, $p<0,001$) after a period of 19 weeks. In the present study, the Cronbach's value of the TAS-20 was 0.83.

Empathy was evaluated with the short form of the Spanish version of the *Empathy Quotient* (EQ; Redondo & Herrero, under review), a 23-item measure developed to assess cognitive and affective aspects of empathy. The items are organized into three subscales: Cognitive Empathy, ($\alpha =.90$), Emotional Reactivity ($\alpha =.63$) and Social Skills ($\alpha =.64$). Each item is ranked on a four-point Likert scale from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 4 (*strongly agree*) scale and a higher score indicates higher levels of empathy. The original version of the EQ has been found to exhibit good psychometric properties (Lawrence, Shaw, Baker, Baron-Cohen, & David, 2004). The Spanish version of the EQ showed a good fit for a three-component model and correlations with other related measures.

IRI Interpersonal Reactivity Index (IRI; Davis, 1980), a 28-item questionnaire with four subscales aimed at measuring different facets of empathy. Each of 4 dimensions is scored on a 5-point Likert scale, from 1 (*does not describe me well*) to 5 (*describes me very well*). This study only included Perspective Taking (PT) subscale, which evaluates the tendency to spontaneously adopt the psychological point of view of others (Davis, 1994), an ability central to detecting mental states. The other subscales were removed for reasons of being more peripheral or for including emotional reactions to other-oriented emotions. The IRI proved good internal and convergent validity, and test-retest reliability, both in its original version (Davis, 1980), and in the Spanish adaptation (Pérez-Albéniz, De Paúl, Etxeberria, Montes & Torres, 2003). In the present sample, Cronbach's alpha for PT subscale was .69.

Procedure

Study procedures were approved by the Research Ethics Board of the University of Deusto (Ref: EKT-8/13-14).

In order to create the adapted version of the RMET, the photographs, option words and glossary were selected from the Spanish adaptation officially published by the Autism

Research Centre (for more information, please visit website: https://www.autismresearchcentre.com/arc_tests). This adaptation was elaborated for the purposes of research and has the approval of the test authors.

Pilot Study

Given that one of the main objectives of the present study was that the test be collectively administered with a limited response time for each of the items, the authors initially conducted a pilot study with 10 students (5 men and 5 women).

The images were projected on a 2.10x1.60 metre screen using 2007 Power-Point software version. In the study, pictures were presented with four options, one in each corner of the picture (one being the target one and the others being foils) and the glossary was also integrated, as illustrated in Figure 1. Thus, together with the options, a synonym or a short definition (as provided by the Autism Research Centre), was also included. Participants had to choose one option from the answer sheet. The instructions preserved the format of the original version of the test. After providing them, participants gave their answers while the experimenter was measuring their response times for each picture. 20 seconds was the longest time taken by only one of the participants for one of items. All the other participants answered faster than this. Therefore, 20 seconds were estimated to be enough for participants to observe the pictures properly, read the options, think about them and select the correct one without speeding up the process. Consequently, the Power-Point was programmed to automatically and successively display photographs every 20 seconds.

After this, participants in the normative sample completed the RMET Spanish adapted version and a package of questionnaires during regular classes. The evaluator provided instructions concerning how the questions must be answered and the need to respond to each item within 20 seconds. Participants in the clinical sample did this individually, in their treatment centres. The size of the screen was maintained without variation with all the groups. The distance between screen and participant, and the fact that all them could clearly see the screen, were especially controlled factors.

The study was presented as a study on health and emotions in students. Students were told that they could withdraw from the study at any point during the assessment, and that participation was completely voluntary. They all gave their consent except two participants who refused to do it and consequently did not take part in it. All participants in the clinical sample, and their parents in the case of minors (those under 18), gave their written informed consent to participate in the study. The study protocol was presented to the Scientific Ethical Committee and the Supervising Board of the centres, neither of which had further remarks on the subject.

[Figure 1]

Data Analysis

Data analysis comprised six steps. In the first, a Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was performed in order to verify the original structure of the questionnaire, so that the

36 items were grouped into three factors (positive, negative and neutral emotions), and alternatively into a single factor. In this case the Lisrel 8.80 software was used (Jöreskog & Sörbom, 1997), and the method for estimation of the parameters was the diagonally weighted least squares (DWLS), as it is the most recommendable method when multivariate normality is not guaranteed (Míndrila, 2010). The model was assessed through several goodness of fit indices, as follows: firstly, the χ^2 / df ratio, with values below 2 indicating good fit (Brooke, Russell, & Price, 1988); the Root Means Squared of Error Approximation (RMSEA), acceptable values being below .06 (Browne & Cudeck, 1992); and the Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI), the Comparative Fit Index (CFI) and the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI), with values above .95 indicating good fit (Hu & Bentler, 1999).

Secondly, given that the previous CFA did not confirm the original structure (see Results section), a Parallel Analysis (PA) of the items was conducted through Factor 10.4.01 software (Lorenzo-Seva & Ferrando, 2013), with the aim of selecting the items for the Spanish version and of verifying their factorial distribution. This analysis was based on the polychoric correlation matrix, as the items were dichotomous. Bayes modal estimation procedure was followed to get this matrix (Choi, Kim, Chen, & Dannels, 2011). Then, the optimal implementation of PA (Timmerman & Lorenzo-Seva, 2011) was used for determining the number of dimensions and the Unweighted Least Squares (ULS) procedure for factor extraction. Next, Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) was calculated to test the model fit, with values above .90 indicating a good fit (Bentler & Bonett, 1980). After the PA, having selected the items based on factorial loadings, a CFA was conducted to verify the final structure, with the same specification as the previous CFA. Finally, reliability (internal consistency) of the final scale was analyzed through both the Cronbach's α and the construct reliability index (ρ) for the whole sample. Besides, internal consistency for each one of the three groups was also analyzed, but in this case only Cronbach's α was reported, because the sample size of the groups was too small to conduct a CFA to calculate the construct reliability index.

In the third step, convergent validity was tested by calculating Pearson's r correlation coefficients with other measures of empathy and alexithymia.

In the fourth step, differences in RMET scores were analyzed by gender and clinical diagnosis. Healthy women, anorexic women and healthy men were compared through a one-way ANOVA. In this case, both signification and effect size (η^2) were calculated. Effect sizes were interpreted according to the Cohen's criterion, so that values below .04 are considered low, between .04 and .14 are medium, and above .14 large (Cohen, 1988). Bonferroni Post-Hoc test was conducted to search for specific differences among the three groups.

In the fifth, a hierarchical multiple regression was conducted with the variables that had been significantly associated with RMET in order to analyze the amount of variance explained, and to determine the variables that remain significantly associated after controlling for the common variance among predictors.

Finally, the capability of the RMET to discriminate between anorexic and healthy women in comparison with the capability of the other variables was analyzed. With this aim, both anorexic and health women were compared in each of the measures through t-

tests. Effect sizes (Cohen's d , which was transformed into Pearson's r) were computed, and the 95% interval of confidence of the r was computed in order to verify whether there were significantly higher differences between the two groups in some of the variables. When two intervals have no value in common it can be concluded that there are significant differences between both of them.

Results

Firstly, a CFA was conducted in order to verify the original structure of the questionnaire. The results suggested that the three factor solution did not fit satisfactorily to the data, $\chi^2 / df = 4.17$; RMSEA = .082 (90% C.I.: .079 - .086); NNFI = 1.19; CFI = 1.00; GFI = .83. Alternatively, another CFA was conducted to verify whether a single factor solution fitted better. The results showed that it did not fit satisfactorily, $\chi^2 / df = 4.22$; RMSEA = .083 (90% C.I.: .080 - .086); NNFI = 1.00; CFI = 1.19; GFI = .83.

Secondly, a PA analysis was conducted for the three hypothesized factors (positive, negative and neutral emotions). However, the results suggested only one factor and PA was re-run with this specification. Items loading lower than .25 were removed, yielding 19 items above this criterion with a good fit (GFI = .93). A CFA was subsequently conducted with these 19 items, showing a good fit of the model to the data, $\chi^2 / df = 0.90$; RMSEA = .000 (90% C.I.: .000 - .015); NNFI = 1.00; CFI = 1.00; GFI = .98. Item description and factorial loadings are shown in Table 1. As can be observed, of the final 19 items, 11 were emotions represented by men and 8 by women. Moreover, the percentage of correct answers ranged between 67.8% (Skeptical) and 94.9% (Contented). Finally, factor loadings ranged from .29 and .65. The factor showed low reliability indices on the whole sample ($\alpha = .56$, $\rho = .59$) as well as in the healthy men group ($\alpha = .64$), in the healthy women group ($\alpha = .46$), and in the anorexic women group ($\alpha = .32$).

[Table 1]

Thirdly, bivariate correlations among the RMET and the other variables were calculated. Results are shown in Table 2. As can be observed, RMET score was significantly correlated with almost all the other measures (except for the Difficulty Describing Feelings subscale of the TAS), with effect sizes ranging from $|.08|$ to $|.21|$. In the case of alexithymia, negative correlations were obtained, while in the case of the Perspective Taking subscale of the IRI and the EQ subscales (empathy variables) the coefficients were positive. Besides, in general terms, all the other measures were significantly related to each other.

[Table 2]

Fourthly, differences in RMET were tested by gender and clinical diagnosis. A significant and medium effect size was obtained in the ANOVA, $F(2, 470) = 21.86, p < .001, \eta^2 = .09$. The Bonferroni Post-Hoc test showed that healthy women ($M = 15.72, SD = 2.15$) scored higher than both anorexic women ($M = 14.66, SD = 2.13, p = .030$) and healthy men ($M = 14.03, SD = 3.03, p < .001$). Finally, anorexic women and healthy men did not differ in their scores ($p = .481$).

Based on these previous results, a 4-step hierarchical multiple regression was built. In the first step, a gender / clinical diagnostic variable was introduced, considering the same three categories as in the previous analysis (healthy women, anorexic women and healthy men). In the second step, Perspective Taking subscale of the IRI was introduced. In the third step, the three factors of the EQ were added, and in the fourth one, alexithymia variables were included (Difficulty Identifying Feelings and Externally Oriented Thinking from the TAS, as they both significantly correlated with the RMET). Results are detailed in Table 3. As can be observed, the predictor variables explained the 13% variance of the RMET score. Only the gender / health group variable and the empathy variables made a significant contribution to the total amount of the explained variance. The highest beta values corresponded to the gender / health group variable even in the last step of the model.

[Table 3]

Finally, the capability of the RMET to discriminate between anorexic and healthy women in comparison with the capability of the other variables was analysed. The results are shown in Table 4. As can be observed, the RMET discriminated better than the cognitive factor of the EQ and worse than TAS subscales and its total score (except for the external thinking factor).

[Table 4]

Discussion

The aim of this study was to examine the validity and factor structure of the Spanish version of the RMET. Furthermore, additional adaptations were made to the instrument to facilitate its administration in large samples.

As expected, the initial CFA showed that the original 36-item structure was not acceptable; neither for the three factor solution, nor for the single factor one. Unlike other versions that have maintained the original 36-item structure (Vellante et al., 2013; Yildirim et al., 2011) this version includes a smaller number of items, possibly due to cultural differences.

In a second step, a PA was conducted to explore the best factorial solution. This analysis provided evidence that the RMET can be effectively scored as a single factor, which could be labeled as “emotion recognition”. However, the hypothesized three factor model based on the emotional valence of the items (positive, negative or neutral; Maurage et al., 2011) was discarded. This implied that the valence of the emotion may not be relevant in order to be correctly identified.

The final result showed that 19 items out of 36 reached the minimally acceptable threshold for factor loading and the model fit was excellent. To verify this structure, a CFA was conducted with these 19 items, showing a good fit of the model to the data. These results are consistent with the study conducted by Vellante et al. (2013), to our knowledge the only that has provided evidence about these psychometric characteristics. As expected, the resulting factor showed a low internal consistency according to both the Cronbach’s alpha and the construct reliability index in both the whole sample and the three sub-samples (men, healthy women and anorexic women). Other, similar research, has also obtained low coefficients (Harkness et al., 2010; Yildirim et al., 2011). Furthermore, most of the studies where psychometric properties of this questionnaire were tested have not reported internal consistency (Fernández-Abascal, et al., 2013). Finally, to our knowledge, no studies have analysed internal consistency in specific sub-samples, as the current study does.

The RMET showed concurrent validity as was evident from the correlations found with measures of empathy and alexithymia. As expected, the RMET positively correlated with the PT subscale of the IRI and the EQ and its subscales, but negatively with alexithymia. This inverse relationship may be understandable due to the fact that the abilities underlying these concepts can somehow be considered opposites. Consistent with some previous research (e.g., Ali & Chamorro-Premuzic, 2010; Declerck & Bogaert, 2008) the RMET correlation with the selfreport measures of empathy was low. These results indicate that self-report measures may not be used interchangeably with the RMET as an indicator of empathy, as had been theoretically suggested in the past. It is widely known that empathy involves both an affective and a cognitive component. The former relates to an individual having an appropriate emotional response to the mental state of another, and the latter largely overlaps with the concepts of “mindreading” or “theory of mind” (Allison, Baron-Cohen, Wheelwright, Stone, & Muncer, 2011; Baron-Cohen & Wheelwright, 2004). However, cognitive processes

involved in cognitive empathy (such as role-taking, switching attention to take another's perspective, or "decentering"; Baron-Cohen & Wheelwright, 2004) may be better evaluated with the RMET. In fact, the RMET can be considered an index of performance, while the other measures are based on the interpretation (sometimes not very accurate) the subject makes about his/her ability. Accordingly, some researchers have criticized self-report measures of empathy because they believe that they are influenced by a social desirability bias (e.g., Eisenberg & Fabes, 1990; Eisenberg & Lennon, 1983). Participants may not respond truthfully to the questions; rather, they may report tendencies that they perceive to be socially desirable (Eisenberg, Fabes, Bustamante, & Mathy, 1987). However, given that a correlation (albeit low) appears, further consideration of such empathic belief-ability gaps must be taken into account.

With regard to differences among groups, analysis reported healthy females were superior to males in RMET and to anorexic women; however, interestingly, there were no significant differences between healthy men and the anorexic group. Several studies have shown differences between healthy women and women suffering from anorexia in RMET and other emotional tasks, with better results for the first group (Bora & Köse, 2016; De Sampaio et al., 2013). These differences are seen to be persistent even when patients are recovered, suggesting that difficulty with emotion recognition appears to have traits associated with their lifelong history, and not states that remit when the individual successfully recovers from the illness (Harrison, Tchanturia, & Treasure, 2010). On the other hand, differences between anorexic and normative women were higher in alexithymia than in theory of mind. Recent studies have demonstrated relevant differences in this variable between anorexic and normative women (Schmelkin, et al., 2017; Westwood, Kerr-Gaffney, Stahl, & Tchanturia, 2017), so this variable could discriminate between anorectic and healthy women even better than theory of mind. Finally, the magnitude of the difference in theory of mind between anorexic and normative groups of women were similar to the difference found in empathy, as measured by both the Interpersonal Reactivity Index and the Empathy Quotient. In this last case the differences were due to the social skills factor. In this sense, research has shown differences in this variable between anorexic and healthy women in social skills (Patel, Tchanturia, & Harrison, 2016), and has proposed that it could be a protective factor against eating disorders (Lazaro, et al., 2011; Uzunian & Vitalle, 2015).

However, although men frequently tend to perform worse in RMET than women, as can be observed in the original study (Baron-Cohen et al., 2001) and in some other studies (Hallerbäck et al., 2009; Yildirim et al., 2011), none of them reveals that their difficulty could be comparable to clinical groups', such as people suffering from anorexia.

Finally, a Hierarchical Multiple Regression Model was used to isolate the predictors which have significant influence on the results in the RMET. Results showed that only gender/health group and Cognitive Empathy and Social Skills remained as significant predictors of the dependent variable and accounted for a moderate amount of the total variance. This implies that when relationships among the predictor variables are controlled; gender, healthy/ clinical sample and self-reported cognitive empathy and social skills are the only variables that remain significant, although the effect sizes (beta coefficients) were lower in the case of both cognitive empathy and social skills than in the case of gender and healthy / clinical sample. This suggests discriminant validity for the RMET, as theoretically related variables (such as alexithymia), which had been

significantly correlated with RMET, lose significance. These results suggest that psychological intervention with anorexic people should include specific treatment for theory of mind.

Despite the good results of the study, there are some limitations that future studies should address. Firstly, as the language knowledge of mental states may be relevant to the correct performance in the test (Baron-Cohen et al., 2001), a language test must be included to control this effect. Moreover, although the items were selected from the official Spanish adaptation by the ARC, it is advisable that the test should go through a complete backtranslation process by native English-Spanish speaker professionals. With respect to the items themselves, although the total number of them was reduced to 19; and the proportion of men's faces slightly higher than that of women, introducing the possibility of some kind of bias, one can be sure that those items that remain as part of the test guarantee its validity in assessing ToM. Furthermore, all the other improvements introduced in the second version (such as the number of possible responses, the glossary etc.) were maintained.

Secondly, the normative sample had a high level of education, which is not representative of the Spanish in reality, and had a higher proportion of women. Future studies should include a more representative and varied strata of the population and other clinical groups.

Finally the RMET includes static stimuli, which diminish realism in situations. Future studies might usefully employ more complex and dynamic stimuli of facial expressions, as Facial Emotion Identification Task (Ihnen, Penn, Corrigan, & Martin, 1998), The Reading the Mind in the Voice test (Rutherford, Baron-Cohen, & Wheelwright, 2002) and morphing tasks (Scrimin, Moscardino, Capello, Altoè, & Axia, 2009) do.

Despite the limitations, this study confirms the validity of the RMET as a measure of ToM and recognition of complex emotions that permits a relatively short and inexpensive way of administration in large samples of adults.

Table 1. Items of the Spanish version of the RMET.

Item	Sex	Emotion	%	CI 95%		Factorial	Error of
			Correct	Upper	Lower	Loading	Estimation
2	M	Upset	83.9	80.4	87.4	.65	.54
5	M	Worried	81.6	78.0	85.2	.28	.92
8	M	Despondent	80.0	76.2	83.8	.43	.82
11	M	Regretful	86.2	83.0	89.4	.37	.86
12	M	Sceptical	67.8	63.4	72.2	.34	.89
13	M	Anticipating	91.5	88.9	94.1	.42	.82
14	M	Accusing	74.3	70.2	78.4	.38	.86
15	F	Contemplative	87.4	84.3	90.5	.35	.88
17	F	Doubtful	80.0	76.2	83.8	.33	.89
18	F	Decisive	94.9	92.8	97.0	.58	.66
20	M	Friendly	89.7	86.8	92.6	.43	.82
22	F	Preoccupied	70.8	66.5	75.1	.25	.94
23	M	Defiant	79.5	75.7	83.3	.30	.91
26	M	Hostile	81.1	77.4	84.8	.46	.79
29	F	Reflective	73.6	69.5	77.7	.33	.89
31	F	Confident	72.4	68.2	76.6	.28	.92
34	F	Distrustful	77.0	73.0	81.0	.34	.88
35	F	Nervous	72.6	68.4	76.8	.26	.93
36	M	Suspicious	78.9	75.1	82.7	.31	.90

Note. Item: Number of item according to the original 36-item version; Sex: Sex of the face in the item (M = Male, F = Female); Emotion: Emotion expressed by the face; % Correct: Percentage of correct answers in the current sample; CI 95%: Confidence Interval of the percentage.

Table 2. Correlation coefficients (Pearson's r) among the variables. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviations) of the variables are included

	RMET	IRI	DIF	DDF	EOT	TAS	CE	ER	SS
RMET	-								
IRI	.10*	-							
DIF	-.09*	-.24***	-						
DDF	-.08	-.25***	.67***	-					
EOT	-.21***	-.31***	.24***	.36***	-				
TAS	-.15***	-.34***	.83***	.86***	.63***	-			
CE	.14**	.31***	-.10*	-.22***	-.30***	-.26***	-		
ER	.13**	.37***	-.08	-.25***	-.32***	-.27***	.42***	-	
SS	.21***	.27***	-.41***	-.44***	-.34***	-.51***	.33***	.23***	-
EQ	.20***	.41***	-.23***	-.37***	-.41***	-.42***	.89***	.68***	.62***

Note. RMET: Reading the Mind in the Eyes Test; IRI: Interpersonal Reactivity Index; DIF: Difficulty Identifying Feelings; DDF: Difficulty Describing Feelings; EOT: Externally Oriented Thinking; TAS: Total score in the Toronto Alexithymia Scale; CE: Cognitive Empathy; ER: Emotional Reactivity; SS: Social Skills; EQ: Total score in the Empathy Quotient.

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Table 3. Hierarchical multiple regression for the RMET score

	<i>B</i>	<i>SE B</i>	β
<i>Step 1</i>			
Gender / Health group ¹	-0.84	0.13	-.29***
<i>Step 2</i>			
Gender / Health group ¹	-0.82	0.13	-.28***
Interpersonal Reactivity Index			
<i>Step 3</i>			
Gender / Health group ¹	-0.84	0.14	-.29***
Interpersonal Reactivity Index	0.01	0.03	-.04
Cognitive Empathy	0.06	0.03	.11*
Emotional Reactivity	-0.03	0.04	-.04
Social Skills	0.14	0.05	.13**
<i>Step 4</i>			
Gender / Health group ¹	-0.79	0.14	-.27***
Interpersonal Reactivity Index	0.01	0.03	.00
Cognitive Empathy	0.05	0.03	.10*
Emotional Reactivity	-0.04	0.04	-.05
Social Skills	0.12	0.05	.12*
Difficulty Identifying Feelings	-0.01	0.02	-.01
Externally Oriented Thinking	-0.04	0.03	-.08

Note: ¹: Gender / Health group: 1 = Healthy women; 2 = Anorexic women; 3 = Healthy men.

RMET: $R^2 = .08$ ($p < .001$) in Step 1; $\Delta R^2 = .01$ ($p = .119$) in Step 2; $\Delta R^2 = .03$ ($p = .001$) in Step 3, $\Delta R^2 = .01$ ($p = .251$) in Step 4.

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Table 4. Differences between healthy and anorexic women in the variables

	Anorexic		Healthy		<i>t</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>l.l</i>	<i>u.l</i>
	n = 38		n = 321						
	M	SD	M	SD					
1. RMET	14.66	2.13	15.72	2.15	-2.87*	-0.50	-.24	-.33	-.14
2. EQ Cognitive	11.26	4.84	11.03	4.63	0.29	0.04	.02	-.08	.12
3. EQ Affective	7.11	2.68	7.55	2.35	-1.08	-0.18	-.09	-.19	.01
4. EQ Soc. Skills	5.05	2.42	7.22	2.34	-5.36**	-0.91	-.41	-.49	-.32
5. EQ Total	23.42	7.25	25.79	7.21	-1.91	-0.33	-.16	-.26	-.06
6. TAS Emot. Sig.	22.79	6.49	10.67	6.96	10.22**	1.80	.67	.61	.72
7. TAS Diff. Expr.	19.18	5.47	11.94	6.37	6.72**	1.22	.52	.44	.59
8. TAS Ext. Think.	13.74	5.50	11.33	4.70	2.92*	0.47	.23	.13	.33
9. TAS Total	52.13	12.80	32.30	12.90	8.96**	1.54	.61	.54	.67
10. IRI	23.05	5.65	25.66	4.58	-3.24*	-0.51	-.25	-.34	-.15

Note: 4: EQ Social Skills; 6. TAS Emotional Signals; 7: TAS Difficulties in Expression; 8 TAS

External Thinking

* $p < .01$, ** $p < .001$.

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